

Coronavirus Disease Research Community – COVID-19

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Title: **Forecast of COVID19 infections, UK**

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I have updated the COVID19 infections data in UK on May 20th, forecasting the evolutions of the new cases and deaths, publishing the graphs on the following free blogs:

<https://covid19forecast.blogspot.com/>

<https://euroid19.blogspot.com/>

The same figures are reported here.

The forecast of the total positive cases, according to the Verhulst equation is over 265,000 cases, while the forecast of the total deaths is over 39,000.

The data of the new cases and deaths are showing the trend to decrease.

UK COVID19 DATA & FORECAST May 20th, 2020

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